

WHEN A FOLDER IS NOT A FOLDER

Investigating Complex Composite Content

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Abstract – Generally file formats on modern systems are single byte streams, and there are many tools available to help identify and determine what software is needed to make use of the format. When dealing with formats born on Macintosh systems, a single byte stream is often not all that is needed to make use of the formats. On older Macintosh systems a Type/Creator code and a resource fork are often needed, and on more modern systems there are other challenges that need to be addressed. This paper explores some popular formats and tools that are needed to properly assess and capture important metadata in a preservation workflow. The formats explored in this paper use a complex document package to create a file format.

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I. INTRODUCTION

A few years ago, while I was preparing a collection of files for ingest into our preservation system, a folder caught my eye. Inside the folder was some files with some formats and names which were not like the normal set of files we often found in our processing. At least they were not a set of files we typically kept in our archive. There was a file named PkgInfo with no extension and an index.xml compressed in a GZip. This folder turned out to be a certain type of complex format created on a Macintosh but processed on a Windows computer. This makes identification difficult using tools like DROID, which will identify the contents of the folder and does not pay much attention to the folder itself.

The folder IS a file format. It may have multiple standard formats within, but together they make a unique complex composite format. The contents are standalone formats, but as a group they are something much different.

Identification of these “folders” as a specific file format made us want to understand how to preserve their unique structure and what kind of issues may come up in long term preservation of these folders. This led to the development of strategies to gather technical metadata needed to preserve the integrity and accessibility of the digital objects. To quote Stephen Abrams; *“The concept of representation format permeates all technical aspects of digital repository architecture and is, therefore, the foundation of many, if not all, digital preservation activities. Digital formats need to be understood both as general classes of encodings and in the specific instances of digital objects.”* [1]

II. DOCUMENT PACKAGE

When Apple moved from their traditional classic MacOS to OSX in the early 2000’s, which was based on an Apple-developed, Unix-based system, they made some significant changes to how applications and documents work. They moved away from

Resource Forks and started using Bundles. This was a way to use a folder with a defined structure to store the files needed to execute the software [2].

Bundles could also be used for complex formats used to store document data. It was a similar problem other developers decided to use a ZIP container to solve, but Apple offered a non-compressed method. Apple described the option as, *"If your document file formats are getting too complex to manage because of several disparate types of data, you might consider adopting a package format for your documents. Document packages give the illusion of a single document to users but provide you with flexibility in how you store the document data internally. Especially if you use several different types of standard data formats, such as JPEG, GIF, or XML, document packages make accessing and managing that data much easier."* [3]. This technique was mainly used by Apple developed software but occasionally used by other developers.

Some of the Apple titles and extensions include:

- Pages (.pages)
- Numbers (.numbers)
- Keynote (.key)
- Garageband (.band)
- Logic Pro X (.logicx)
- Textedit (.rtfd)

Some 3rd party software and extensions include:

- Scrivener (.scriv)
- OmniOutliner (.oo3)
- Vmware (.vmwarevm)

The MacOS system was responsible for making the folder appear as a single file. This was handled by registering the software with the systems launch services database, so there is no hidden file, resource, or extended attribute within the folder structure to indicate the folder is a package/bundle. Moving the folder to another Macintosh without having the software installed would cause the same issue you would find moving the folder to a Windows or Linux system. It would simply be a folder with an extension.

III. LOOKING CLOSER

Understanding the problem prompted us to look at our acquisition and assessment process more closely. Instead of moving all digital objects initially to a Windows environment for processing, we needed a solution that allowed us to gather as much

metadata as possible from the original operating system.

Normally once the digital objects had been moved to a location in our processing environment, we would run DROID across the collection to gather important identification information, dates, and checksums for the objects. But as mentioned, running DROID on a folder wouldn't provide the specific information we needed for identification.

We created a script [4] to utilize a tool found in all base MacOS systems; MDLS. MDLS is a command line tool that lists the metadata attributes for a specified file, or in our case a "folder" which identifies as a file. This metadata comes from the Spotlight index, which means that the file must be local in order to retrieve the extensive metadata available. The output from MDLS when pointed to a file on an Apple File System, will include a list of kMDItem's, or Metadata Attribute Keys [5]. These keys can provide a wealth of information that would be lost when moved away from the MacOS. Our script would gather a few of these keys and presents them much like a DROID report; identifying the package format as a file, and providing the name of the format as known to the operating system. The script will also provide us with numerous date stamps and a ContentType. This ContentType is the Apple's more modern use of format identifiers called UTI's or Uniform Type Identifiers [6], used across its platforms. Some kMDItems would look like:

- kMDItemContentCreationDate = 2025-04-06 03:41:46
- kMDItemContentModificationDate = 2025-04-06 03:41:46
- kMDItemContentType = "com.apple.iwork.pages.sffpages"
- kMDItemContentTypeTree = "public.composite-content"
- kMDItemFSName = "iPres-sample.pages"
- kMDItemKind = "Pages Document"

The MacOS even understands this object is a **Composite Content** type, it knows there is mixed embedded content [7].

IV. EXAMPLES

One of the most common formats we run into is the Pages format, which was part of the iWork suite that often came with a new Macintosh. The Package method was only used in the iWork '05, '06, '08, and 2013 versions. This suite was intended to provide the same software you would find in any Office Suite: a word processor (Pages), a spreadsheet (Numbers), and presentation (Keynote). It was first released in 2004, and is still used today, but the formats have

gone through some changes over the different releases.

Other office suite software used a ZIP container to manage the objects. This is helpful if your institution prefers a single file for preservation. The older package formats can be opened and saved with a newer version to help make identification and long-term storage a little easier. If you would like to learn more about each version, you can follow along on my blog [8].

Another example of this format can be found in the Scrivener [9] document format which uses the extension “.scriv”. Scrivener is one example of software not developed by Apple, which uses the bundle format. It has been around for many years, dating back to 2007. It is a word processor and outliner used by writers. The Scrivener documents can include much more than plain text, so the file format uses a package format to store all the needed components to render the format. The developer does have a Macintosh and Windows version with the note that the Windows version is simply a folder and is opened by clicking on the “.scrivx” XML format found inside the folder.

The MDLS tool can tell us a lot about this format on the Macintosh:

```
[thorsted@Thorsted Test Files % mdls Scrivener3-s01.scriv
_KMDItemDisplayNameWithExtensions = "Scrivener3-s01.scriv"
KMDItemAlternateNames = (
    "Scrivener3-s01.scriv"
)
KMDItemContentCreationDate = 2025-03-10 21:25:08 +0000
KMDItemContentCreationDate_Ranking = 2025-03-10 00:00:00 +0000
KMDItemContentModificationDate = 2025-03-12 20:01:14 +0000
KMDItemContentType = "com.literatureandlatte.scrivener3.scriv"
KMDItemContentTypeTree = (
    "com.literatureandlatte.scrivener3.scriv",
    "public.directory",
    "public.item",
    "com.apple.package",
    "public.content",
    "public.composite-content"
)
KMDItemDateAdded = 2025-03-12 20:01:01 +0000
KMDItemDisplayName = "Scrivener3-s01.scriv"
KMDItemDocumentIdentifier = 0
KMDItemFSContentChangeDate = 2025-03-12 20:01:14 +0000
KMDItemFSCreationDate = 2025-03-10 21:25:08 +0000
KMDItemFSCreatorCode = ""
KMDItemFSFinderFlags = 16
KMDItemFSHasCustomIcon = (null)
KMDItemFSInvisible = 0
KMDItemFSIsExtensionHidden = 1
KMDItemFSIsStationery = (null)
KMDItemFSLabel = 0
KMDItemFSName = "Scrivener3-s01.scriv"
KMDItemFSNodeCount = 4
KMDItemFSOwnerGroupID = 1539093546
KMDItemFSOwnerUserID = 504957928
KMDItemFSSize = 25609
KMDItemFSTypeCode = ""
KMDItemInterestingDate_Ranking = 2025-03-12 00:00:00 +0000
KMDItemIsUploaded = 1
KMDItemIsUploading = 0
KMDItemKind = "Scrivener Project"
KMDItemLastUsedDate = 2025-03-10 21:28:57 +0000
KMDItemLastUsedDate_Ranking = 2025-03-10 00:00:00 +0000
KMDItemLogicalSize = 25609
KMDItemPhysicalSize = 57344
KMDItemUseCount = 40
KMDItemUsedDates = (
    "2025-03-10 06:00:00 +0000"
)

```

V. SOLUTIONS

In the past, due to the lack of understanding of this unique format and the lack of definition of our acquisition and assessment, we would end up finding these types of folders altered during the processing and arrangement steps in our workflow. After increasing our understanding, our improved process would most often make format be ZIP compressed and possibly make a PDF to provide easier access to the format. Migration to a PDF/A or an open document format was also considered. However, in my current position and born-digital workflows, I have considered leaving the format as folder. This would only work if all the content is identifiable. Then the metadata discovered through the MDLS software can be included with the object. Another option being considered is the use of a disk image to contain the formats within a file system that retains the rich metadata. When working in the field to capture objects from a donor’s Macintosh, this could be a solution to allow for further assessment at a later time.

VI. CONCLUSION

The process of analyzing and researching the package format has provided us several viable options for consideration. This research has underscored the critical importance of capturing information directly from the source file preferably on the source system. Often, relocating digital objects from their original file systems can lead to the inadvertent loss of critical metadata. This includes metadata found when running MDLS, extended attributes, resource forks and Finder data.

These elements are crucial for maintaining the integrity and accessibility of the digital objects. Understanding the folder structure can also provide guidance on how the data should be or can be stored, maintaining the original order to avoid corruption. Further conversation about best practices for these complex formats is needed in the digital preservation community.

REFERENCES

- [1] <https://doi.org/10.1108/03055720410530997>
- [2] [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bundle_\(macOS\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bundle_(macOS))
- [3] <https://developer.apple.com/library/archive/documentation/CoreFoundation/Conceptual/CFBundles/DocumentationPackages/DocumentPackages.html>

- [4] <https://github.com/thorsted/Born-Digital-Scripts/blob/main/MDLS-parsefolder.py>
- [5] https://developer.apple.com/documentation/corestorage/file_metadata/mditem/common_metadata_attribute_keys
- [6] https://developer.apple.com/library/archive/documentation/FileManagement/Conceptual/understanding_utis/understand_utis_intro/understand_utis_intro.html
- [7] <https://developer.apple.com/documentation/uniformtypeidentifiers/uttypecompositecontent>
- [8] <https://preservation.tylerthorsted.com/2023/09/01/apple-package-format/>
- [9] <https://preservation.tylerthorsted.com/2025/03/21/scrivener/>

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